

BENZOYL CHLORIDE AS A POLAR SOLVENT. PART III. VISUAL TITRATIONS IN BENZOYL CHLORIDE

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Visual titrations in benzoyl chloride between the Lewis acids, stannic chloride and titanium tetrachloride, and solvo-bases, quinoline, α -picoline and dimethylaniline, with the help of reversible indicators, crystal violet, benzanthrone and malachite green, have been carried out and the partial ionic character of the carbon-chlorine bond in benzoyl chloride has been indicated.

In view of the earlier investigations in benzoyl chloride (Paul *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 489, 869; *Curr. Sci.*, 1957, 26, 391) and due to the encouragement provided by the results of acid-base neutralisation reactions in acetyl chloride, studied with the help of indicator dyes (Paul, Singh and Sandhu, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1958, 21, 622), the present endeavour was purposefully conceived. The solvo system benzoyl chloride with respect to its particular acids and bases has already been discussed in Part II (*loc. cit.*). The acid chlorides, organic as well as inorganic, are very reactive substances and usually effect the stability of the indicator dyes if the latter are susceptible to attack. In the case of thionyl chloride, it has been reported (Garber, Pease and Luder, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, 25, 581) that crystal violet is unstable and tolerable results are only obtained if the indicator is added near the expected end-point. Apparently, no such difficulty has been encountered in the titrations of acids and bases in benzoyl chloride when crystal violet, malachite green and benzanthrone are employed as indicators to detect the neutralisation point.

In aqueous solutions crystal violet gives yellow, green and violet colour at p_H 0.1, 1.5 and 3.2 respectively (Rice, Zuffanti and Luder, *ibid.*, 1952, 24, 1022). Similar colour changes in acidic and basic solutions in acetyl chloride, including blue colour in pure acetyl chloride, have been recorded (Paul, Singh and Sandhu, *loc. cit.*). The colour of crystal violet in benzoyl chloride changes in the same sequence when solvo-acids and solvo-bases are added to its solutions in benzoyl chloride. Malachite green gives red and green colour in acidic and basic solutions in benzoyl chloride respectively. The colour of malachite green in aqueous solutions at p_H 0-0.2 is yellow to green and at p_H 11.5-14.0 is blue to colorless (Tomicek, "Chemical Indicators", Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1951, p. 50). In thionyl chloride malachite green has been found to be relatively stable and gives good results in acid-base titrations (Garber, Pease and Luder, *loc. cit.*). The colours of malachite green in aqueous and benzoyl chloride solutions are, however, quite different. Benzanthrone, which has proved to be a potent dye in the study of acid-base reactions in acetyl chloride (Sandhu, private communication), is also remarkably stable in benzoyl chloride and gives a red colour in acidic solutions and a yellow colour in basic solutions. There are meagre data in aqueous solutions for benzanthrone with which the results of these investigations could have been compared. Nevertheless, the results of acid-base neutralisation reactions in benzoyl chloride and acetyl chloride are favourably comparable. In Table I are reported the colours of these indicators in pure benzoyl chloride and in solutions of acids and bases in it.

TABLE I

Indicator.	C_6H_5COCl (solvent).		$TiCl_4$.	$SnCl_4$.	Quinoline.	α -Picoline.	D.M.A.
Crystal violet	Blue	Colour in weak solution	Deep yellow	Yellow	Violet	Violet	Blue
		Colour in conc. solution	Orange-yellow	Orange-yellow	Purple	Purple	Pink
Benzanthrone	Light yellow	Colour in weak solution	Red	Orange-red	Light yellow	Light yellow	Light yellow
		Colour in conc. solution	Blood-red	Red	Do	Do	Greenish yellow
Malachite green	Deep green	Colour in weak solution	Red	Do	Deep green	Deep green	Deep green
		Colour in conc. solution	Deep red	Deep red	Bluish green	Bluish green	Bluish green

D.M.A. = Dimethylaniline.

The reversibility of these indicators in benzoyl chloride has been illustrated by carrying out acid-base titrations with acidic as well as basic solutions as titrants. Generally, the formation of a precipitate results during the titration which in some cases absorbs the indicator temporarily and thus makes the detection of the colour change rather difficult. The reaction mixture was magnetically stirred. The precipitate was allowed to settle down after which the colour change was noted. Sometimes the precipitate was flocculent and required a long time for complete settling down. In such a case, the colour of the supernatant liquid was observed. The results obtained for the titrations of acids and bases with crystal violet, malachite green and benzanthrone are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Titrant.	Substance.	Conc. of the	Wt. of the	Volume of the		Colour of the indicator at the end-point.
		titrant (g. mole/litre).	substance.	titrant solution.	Found. Calc.	
A. Indicator: Crystal violet.						
$SnCl_4$	Quinoline	0.1211	0.0990 g.	3.00 c.c.	3.10 c.c.	Green
	Picoline	0.0808	0.0845	5.60	5.61	Light green
	D.M.A.	0.1126	0.0385	1.70	1.41	Greenish yellow
$TiCl_4$	Quinoline	0.0068	0.0805	3.25	3.22	Green
	α -Picoline	0.0918	0.0743	4.15	4.32	Light green
	D.M.A.	0.0968	0.0275	1.15	1.17	Light yellow
Quinoline	$SnCl_4$	0.1703	0.0200	1.05	0.90	Green
	$TiCl_4$	0.1201	0.0430	3.65	3.76	Greenish blue
α -Picoline	$SnCl_4$	0.1540	0.1065	5.30	5.32	Bluish green
	$TiCl_4$	0.1540	0.0470	3.25	3.21	Do
D.M.A.	$SnCl_4$	0.1061	0.0500	3.70	3.63	Yellowish green
	$TiCl_4$	0.1461	0.0640	2.70	2.74	Bluish green

TABLE II (contd.)

Titrant.	Substance.	Conc. of the titrant		Wt. of the substance.		Volume of the titrant solution.		Colour of the indicator at the end-point.
		(g. mole/litre .				Found.	Calc.	
B. Indicator : Benzanthrone.								
SnCl ₄	Quinoline	0.1211	0.0700	2.30	2.24	Orange-yellow		
	α -Picoline	0.0808	0.0810	5.40	5.39	Do		
	D. M. A.	0.1211	0.0800	2.70	2.73	Dark brown		
TiCl ₄	Quinoline	0.0968	0.1735	7.00	6.04	Orange		
	α -Picoline	0.0928	0.0900	5.20	5.21	Do		
	D.M.A.	0.0968	0.0280	1.15	1.19	Deep orange		
Quinoline	SnCl ₄	0.1407	0.0840	4.35	4.59	Orange-yellow		
	TiCl ₄	0.1703	0.0415	2.50	2.56	Do		
α -Picoline	SnCl ₄	0.2027	0.0780	2.75	2.80	"		
	TiCl ₄	0.2027	0.0590	2.95	3.00	"		
D. M. A.	SnCl ₄	0.2461	0.0440	1.30	1.37	Dark brown		
	TiCl ₄	0.1061	0.0420	4.11	4.16	Orange-yellow		
C Indicator : Malachite green.								
SnCl ₄	Quinoline	0.0758	0.0710	3.70	3.63	Dirty green		
	α -Picoline	0.0758	0.0340	2.50	2.41	Do		
	D. M. A.	0.0758	0.0290	1.90	1.58	"		
TiCl ₄	Quinoline	0.1087	0.0660	3.50	2.35	"		
	α -Picoline	0.1087	0.0500	3.60	2.47	"		
	D. M. A.	0.1087	0.0290	2.20	1.10	Green		
Quinoline	SnCl ₄	0.2946	0.0360	0.95	0.94	Do		
	TiCl ₄	0.2946	0.0520	1.50	1.85	"		
α -Picoline	SnCl ₄	0.1971	0.0310	1.25	1.20	Deep green		
	TiCl ₄	0.1971	0.0480	1.45	2.14	Do		
D. M. A.	SnCl ₄	0.0944	0.0490	3.00	3.98	"		
	TiCl ₄	0.0944	0.0390	2.80	4.34	Bluish green		

D. M. A. = Dimethylaniline.

The colour of the indicators at the end-points differs slightly with each acid-base pair which is probably related to the relative strengths of the acids and bases. But there is no marked departure from the usual colour which could have helped in arranging these acids and bases in the order of their relative strengths in benzoyl chloride (cf. acetyl chloride, Paul, Singh and Sandhu, *loc. cit.*). However, titanium tetrachloride appears to be a weak acid in benzoyl chloride (Table II).

The colour changes of the indicators in aqueous solutions are explained by taking into consideration the existence of ionic species such as hydrogen and hydroxyl ions, which are doubtlessly established. The acid-base titrations in benzoyl chloride can be explained on the basis of the presence of benzoylium and chloride ions which are produced in its solution when solvo-acids or solvo-bases are added to them. In the case of acetyl chloride, it has already been suggested that these colour changes are due to the presence of acetylum ions and chloride ions, the existence of which has been quite candidly emphasised (Paul and Sandhu, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 262). So, on the basis of analogy and work already done on benzoyl chloride, these colour changes of indicators in the presence of Lewis acids and bases can be generally expressed as due to the following mode of its ionisation :

A neutralisation reaction can therefore be represented as :

This mode of ionisation of benzoyl chloride brings it in line with acetyl chloride and helps in comparing its potentialities as a polar solvent with water. The ionisation of benzoyl chloride is supported by conductometric work (Johar, private communication) and also by comparing its behaviour with non-polar solvents such as carbon tetrachloride and chlorobenzene. It has been found that in these non-polar solvents, quantitative assessment of the acids and bases cannot be made as the end-points are not sharp and it requires quite an excess of the acid or the base to bring about the required colour change. Moreover, the reaction has been found to be very slow as compared to that in water and benzoyl chloride, where the existence of ions is postulated.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Benzoyl chloride, the Lewis acids and the bases were purified as described in earlier papers (*loc. cit.*). For the titrations, a modified burette with a reservoir at the upper end for stocking the titrant solution was fitted into a titration flask, with a side tube for calcium chloride guard tube. All precautions were taken to avoid contamination of the solutions with moisture.

A weighed amount of the substance to be titrated was added to 20 c.c. of benzoyl chloride, placed in the titration flask; 3-5 mg. of indicator was added and the reaction mixture was stirred with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The titrant solution, which was prepared in a 100 c.c. measuring flask in a dry box, was added dropwise from the burette. On the appearance of any perceptible change in colour, the stirring of the reaction mixture was stopped, and the precipitate was allowed to settle and the colour of the supernatant liquid was noted. The titration was again continued and the burette readings at particular colour changes were recorded. The results are recorded in Table II.

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